

Efficient Edge-to-Cloud Workload Management

Title	ENACT Secure and Sovereign Distributed Data Storage
Document Owners	CERTH
Contributors	ICE, UOWM, SIE, UPV, MOG, EITB, OSO, INNO, FUJ
Dissemination	Public (PU)
Date	30/06/2025
Version	V1.0

Version History

Nr.	Date	Author (Organization)	Description
0.1	06/03/2025	Ioanna Kapetanidou, Alexandros Nizamis (CERTH)	Deliverable structure and Work Distribution
0.2	02/05/2025	Ioanna Kapetanidou (CERTH)	Input to Introduction, Position in the ENACT Architecture, Technical Components and Release Summary
0.3	16/05/2025	Thomas Lagkas, Athanasios Liatifis, Dimitrios Pliatsios, Anna Triantafyllou, Panagiotis Sarigiannidis (UOWM), Mafalda Santos and Eva Mata (MOG)	Input to sections 7.1.1, 7.3.1
0.4	23/05/2025	Juan Gascón Repullés, Matilde Julián Seguí (UPV)	Contributions to sections 6.3.2, 6.3.3
0.5	26/05/2025	Bartłomiej Bukala, Szymon Byczek, Aleksandra Swoboda (FUJ)	Contributions to section 7.3.3
0.6	02/06/2025	Mihnea Lopataru, Gabriel Danciu (SIE)	Contributions to sections 7.2, 7.3.4
0.7	03/06/2025	Cristina Domínguez (INNO), Larraitz Eguren (EITB), Eneko Aguirre (Osoigo), Vesna Kobal (Arctur), Thanasis Kotsiopoulos, Paschalis Bizopoulos (CERTH), Oscar Garcia, Ross Campell, Usman Wajid (ICE)	Contributions to section 7.3.2, Revisions to sections 7.2.1, 7.2.2
0.8	13/06/2025	Alexandros Nizamis (CERTH)	Review and revisions
0.9	23/06/2025	Ioanna Kapetanidou (CERTH)	Version for internal review
1.0	30/06/2025	Ioanna Kapetanidou, Alexandros Nizamis (CERTH)	Submitted version

Disclaimer

The content of this deliverable has been prepared in compliance with the requirements of the European Commission for the management, organization, documentation, and sharing of research data generated or collected during the course of the ENACT project. The nature of this deliverable is public (PU) hence its content can be shared with consortium partners and general public.

Acknowledgement

The ENACT project is funded by the Horizon Europe Program of the European Commission under **Grant Agreement 101135423**.

Content

1. Executive Summary	7
2. Introduction.....	7
2.1 Purpose and scope of the deliverable	7
2.2 Relation to other WPs and tasks	7
2.3 Structure of the deliverable	8
3. Requirements Analysis	8
3.1 Requirement analysis regarding Data Access & Sharing Interfaces.....	8
3.2 Requirement analysis regarding Data Manager & Data Stores.....	9
4. Technical Objectives.....	10
5. Position in the ENACT Architecture.....	11
6. Technical Components.....	12
6.1 Data Access and Sharing Interfaces	14
6.1.1 Overview	14
6.1.2 Technological Description	14
6.1.3 Development Status	19
6.2 Data Manager	21
6.2.1 Overview	21
6.2.2 Technological Description	21
6.2.3 Development Status	23

6.3	Data Stores.....	24
6.3.1	Overview	24
6.3.2	Technological Description	24
6.3.3	Development Status	26
7.	Use cases & Integration.....	27
7.1	Interconnections with ENACT components.....	27
7.1.1	Telemetry Data Collector & Monitoring Engine.....	27
7.2	Application Programming Model.....	30
7.2.1	AI Forecaster & Application Controller	31
7.2.2	Virtual Training Environment	32
7.3	Data Space Integration into Pilot UCs.....	32
7.3.1	UC#1: Media Broadcasting: Hyper-distributed Media Content Processing.....	33
7.3.2	UC#2: Enhanced Live Experience: Transforming rowing Regattas La Concha Flag Tracking with VR Technologies	33
7.3.3	UC#3: Hyper-distributed Data Processing for Fujitsu's Mobility Digital Twin Initiative.....	33
7.3.4	Storing SDK-generated video streaming application metadata in the ENACT Data Space	34
8.	Release Summary	39
9.	Conclusions.....	40
10.	Annex: Questionnaire on Storage Needs.....	40

List of figures

Figure 1: Data Layer position in ENACT Architecture	12
Figure 2: ENACT Distributed Storage Overview	14
Figure 3: Asset sharing workflow through soivity connectors.....	15
Figure 4: soivity EDC UI - Policy Creation.....	16
Figure 5: soivity EDC UI - Client Catalog Browser	17
Figure 6: soivity EDC UI - Contracts.....	17
Figure 7: soivity EDC UI - Client Initiating Transfer dialog.....	18
Figure 8: soivity EDC UI - Transfer History.....	18
Figure 9: ENACT data source	19
Figure 10: Trusted Communication Establishment between	22
Figure 11: ENACT Keycloak Server	23
Figure 12: Questionnaire respondents.....	24
Figure 13: Answers to "Where will data be stored?"	25
Figure 14: ENACT MinIO object store in CERTH server.....	27
Figure 15: uowm-data policy creation	28
Figure 16: Data offer for TDCME data.....	29
Figure 17: Negotiating TDCME's data offer	29
Figure 18: Transferring TDCME data to Data Space	30
Figure 19: APM-Data Space interaction for code object storing.....	31
Figure 20: Data Layer-AI Forecaster & Application Controller Interactions.....	32
Figure 21: Data Layer-VTE Interaction	32
Figure 22: Workflow 1: Data Uploading.....	35
Figure 23: Workflow 2: Data retrieval	36
Figure 24: Video Data Offer	37
Figure 25: Connector Usage Policy	37
Figure 26: Retrieved Asset	38
Figure 27: Data Storage questionnaire (Questions 1,2)	41
Figure 28: Data Storage questionnaire (Questions 3-10).....	42
Figure 29: Data Storage questionnaire (Questions on pilot data).....	43

List of tables

Table 1: ENACT Distributed Storage Nodes	13
Table 2: Connector API Endpoints.....	20

List of abbreviations

Abbreviation	Full Term
APM	Application Programming Model
AI	Artificial Intelligence
API	Application Programming Interface
CCC	Cognitive Compute Continuum
CRUD	Create, Read, Update, Delete
DAPS	Dynamic Attribute Provisioning Service
DAT	Dynamic Attribute Token
DID	Decentralized Identifier
DSL	Domain-Specific Language
EDC	Eclipse Data Connector
IAM	Identity and Access Management
IDS	International Data Spaces
IDSA	International Data Spaces Association
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
KQL	Kibana Query Language
ODRL	Open Digital Rights Language
RAM	Reference Architecture Model
SDK	Software Development Kit
TDCME	Telemetry Data Collector & Monitoring Engine
VC	Verifiable Credential
VTE	Virtual Training Environment
VR	Virtual Reality
WP	Work Package
UC	Use Case

1. Executive Summary

This deliverable documents the development activities carried out in Task 4.4 “Secure and Sovereign Distributed Data Storage”. Essentially, this task delivers the ENACT Data and Object Space. This space is being implemented in the ENACT Data Layer which includes the Data Access and Sharing Interfaces, the Data Manager, and the distributed storage nodes.

First of all, D4.3 includes a requirement analysis section which describes briefly the steps that have been taken towards covering the components’ functional requirements defined in WP2. Furthermore, this deliverable delves into the technological background of each component, laying out the employed technologies and presenting the up-to-date development status per component. The technical progress is further reported by delineating the integration of the Data Layer with the Telemetry Data Collector & Monitoring Engine (TDCME) for storing historical telemetry data, the Application Programming Model (APM) for object sharing, the AI Forecaster and the Application Controller for storing historical forecasts to be used for application optimizations, and the Virtual Training Environment to feed it with historical telemetry data and forecasts to assist in AI training, describing the considered interconnections and dataflows.

Last but not least, the deliverable touches upon the usage of the ENACT Data Space in the context of the ENACT hyper-distributed pilot applications, namely, media broadcasting, enhanced live experience with VR technologies and data processing in digital twins. An early integration of the first pilot with the ENACT Data Space is also outlined: this process includes the generation of metadata of the video streaming application using the SDK, and the storing and sharing of such metadata through the Data Space.

2. Introduction

2.1 Purpose and scope of the deliverable

This deliverable covers the components comprising the ENACT Data Layer, namely (i) the Data Access and Sharing Interfaces, (ii) the Data Manager, and (iii) the distributed Data Stores. For each component, the deliverable presents the underlying technological choices and to report on their development status as of M18. The reported development activities are performed with the aim to deliver the ENACT distributed storage system, contributing to the achievement of Milestone 4, i.e., initial ENACT core components availability. Furthermore, D4.3 describes the positioning of the Data Layer components within the ENACT architecture as well as their interactions with other components. Finally, it also showcases how the Data Layer components are intended to be employed in the pilot use cases, hence demonstrating their practical integration in real-world scenarios.

2.2 Relation to other WPs and tasks

The technical developments documented in this deliverable are based on the technical requirements and specifications of the components defined in WP2. An analysis of how the defined requirements are being addressed is presented. Moreover, any technical updates on the components presented here will be addressed in the context of T7.3.

The implemented ENACT Data Store and Data Space will be visible in the CCC graphs generated by the Dynamic Graph Modeller (T4.2). The stored assets should also conform with the data models that have been specified in T4.2. Moreover, the secure data management practices employed in T4.4 complement the security assessments provided by the Security Risk Modeller in T4.3 to reinforce the overall ENACT CCC security posture.

Furthermore, this deliverable is closely interrelated with the development activities carried out in WP6 and WP5, as it directly interfaces with key components such as the Application Programming Model, the Application Controller, and the Telemetry Data Collector & Monitoring Engine, developed under Tasks 6.1, 6.2, and 6.3, respectively. It also interacts with the AI Forecaster and the Virtual Training Environment developed under Tasks 5.1 and 5.4.

In addition, D4.3 is linked to WP3, reporting on how the specifications and data provided by the pilots are taken into consideration. Last but not least, any activities concerning the dissemination of the technical outcomes included in this deliverable fall under the scope of WP8.

2.3 Structure of the deliverable

The rest of the deliverable is organized as follows: Section 3 provides an analysis of the approach taken in order to address the technical requirements that have been defined for the components. In Section 4, we summarize the technical objectives guiding the development of the ENACT Data Layer. In Section 5, we show how this layer is positioned within the ENACT architecture. Section 6 presents the technical description of the developed components, including both the technologies considered and the development status per component, while Section 7 demonstrates the interaction of the Data Space with other ENACT components as well as its use in the pilots. An indicative integration scenario is also presented. Section 8 provides a summary of the release of the delivered results and Section 9 sets out the conclusions.

3. Requirements Analysis

In this section, we introduce the requirements of the Data Layer as defined in WP2 in order to achieve the main objective of implementing a distributed data and object storage system capable of storing historical telemetry and infrastructure data across the ENACT CCC in a distributed, yet reliable and scalable manner. The final storage system must be compatible with the Data Space concept and enable the efficient execution of CRUD operations on assets, including both data and objects. We hereafter provide a brief overview of how these requirements are addressed as of M18. The requirements are expected to be fully covered by M36 in the context of T7.3 and the respective outcomes will be presented in D7.3.

3.1 Requirement analysis regarding Data Access & Sharing Interfaces

[C06.1 - The Data Store must support querying and filtering of data using an API, allowing users to perform retrieval operations.](#)

A node.js API has been implemented which supports CRUD operations, including assets (data & objects) retrieval. Moreover, a filtering function has been defined to filter stored metadata to retrieve matching assets from the corresponding data store to satisfy users' GET requests.

[C06.2 - The Data Store should support querying data using query language, allowing users to perform retrieval operations.](#)

Currently, Elasticsearch is the main database technology considered in ENACT. The interaction with deployed Elasticsearch instances is achieved using the Elasticsearch Query DSL (Domain Specific Language) query language to perform query-based search and data retrieval.

[C06.3 - The Data Store must support querying and provision of data by using Data Space Connectors.](#)

Sovity Data Space Connectors have been selected as the most suitable connector implementation. Connectors have been setup, integrated with the ENACT Keycloak server and exposed for intercommunication with other components.

[C06.4 - The ENACT data access & sharing interfaces must interoperate with various data sources spread across the computing layers](#)

A collection of API calls has been implemented so that the interfaces are easily accessible from any node across the CCC.

3.2 Requirement analysis regarding Data Manager & Data Stores

[C07.1 - The ENACT Distributed Data Storage must be able to store telemetry, resource, and deployment data reliably across multiple nodes in a distributed manner.](#)

The integration with Telemetry Data Collector & Monitoring Engine (TDCME) provides the Data Stores with telemetry, resource and deployment data. Distributed storage nodes are being considered. In addition, a questionnaire was circulated among partners and information on the layers on which pilot data will be stored and the respective storage technologies has been gathered and are taken into account.

[C07.2 - The ENACT Data Storage could enable the storage and sharing of Objects as well, besides actual data storage and sharing.](#)

Integration with the Application Programming Model (APM) and the Software Development Kit (SDK) to allow for the exchange of code objects is in progress.

[C07.3 - ENACT Data Store must support access control policies to restrict access to sensitive data and ensure that only authorized users can execute CRUD operations.](#)

The Data Manager has been integrated with a Keycloak server and thus, supports the enforcement of access control rules. Certain roles need to be created.

[C07.4 - The ENACT distributed data store must be able to scale to accommodate growing data volumes, increasing user traffic, and changing workload demands.](#)

Relevant test case scenarios have been defined and performance tests will be performed in the coming months, considering also pilot data.

[C07.5 - ENACT distributed data store must offer low latency in CRUD operations.](#)

In the current implementation, this objective is achieved. Further performance testing considering growing data volumes and heavy user load will be performed to validate that latency remains acceptable.

[C07.6 - ENACT Data Store must be able to store and handle metadata](#)

A metadata manager subcomponent has been defined, supporting data indexing to facilitate lookup and retrieval functions. Also, an initial validation of metadata handling scenario has been designed and is being implemented in collaboration with SIE and Pilot 1 (MOG).

[C07.7 - ENACT Data Store must support various data types and formats \(e.g. json, csv, files, audio/video files\)](#)

A questionnaire was circulated among partners and information on expected pilot data formats and volumes has been collected and is taken into account. For instance, our MinIO instance currently stores .json files provided by the telemetry service as well as .csv files generated in the context of the first pilot by the SDK.

4. Technical Objectives

This deliverable is focused on the development activities of the ENACT Data Layer. The ENACT Data Layer aims to create a secure, sovereign, and interoperable environment for data and object sharing across the ENACT continuum. The main technical objectives of this layer are:

1. To provide Data and Object Sharing mechanisms that facilitate the storage and retrieval of historical telemetry data, support the sharing of datasets required for training AI models, and enable the exchange of code objects to assist application development and deployment.
2. To establish a Secure ENACT Data Space by implementing Dataspace Connectors that enable secure, policy-based data exchange between multiple parties, providing mechanisms for asset owners to define and enforce fine-grained access policies, and ensuring that all data transfers between participants are protected against unauthorized access.
3. Interoperability with existing Data Spaces by building upon well-established Connector implementations and utilizing standard protocols for data exchange to ensure adherence to International Data Spaces (IDS) and Gaia-X specifications.
4. Identity and Access Management through integration of the Dynamic Attribute Provisioning Service (DAPS) with Keycloak to ensure authentication mechanisms are in place, and to validate and enforce access rights for secure connector-to-connector communication.
5. To offer comprehensive API Interfaces including endpoints for asset management, contract negotiation, data transfer, and policy management to facilitate interaction with the Data Space.
6. Distributed Storage capabilities by interconnecting various storage resources, maintaining metadata about stored assets to facilitate discovery and retrieval, and tracking the health and availability of storage resources.

Overall, our work directly supports the core objectives of WP4 by contributing to the realization of an integrated compute continuum enhanced through mechanisms for dynamic data management across the computing layers, as well as data management policies that ensure data interoperability and trustworthy and secure cross-layer communication in the CCC.

Finally, the technical outcomes described in the following deliverable sections contribute to the first ENACT operational objective (OO#1), i.e., “Provide mechanisms to optimise the execution of distributed applications (across Edge to Cloud) and proactively balance, and optimise the compute swarm according to needs and opportunities in the CCC”. This is achieved through the development of the ENACT Secure and Sovereign Distributed Data Storage system, which ensures data sovereignty, locality, availability and accessibility across the ENACT continuum to ultimately accommodate dynamic demands and functional requirements of the ENACT CCC.

5. Position in the ENACT Architecture

The main objective of the ENACT Data Layer is to store the historical telemetry data, datasets used for AI training as well as code objects, but also to support access control. This layer offers a distributed Data and Object Space, which ensures secure data assets and object sharing, interoperability and sovereignty across the ENACT continuum.

As shown in Figure 1, the ENACT Data Layer consists of the Data Access and Sharing Interfaces, the Data Manager and the Data Stores.

The Data Access and Sharing Interfaces serve as the Data Layer endpoint, acting as an intermediary between the Data Layer and other ENACT architectural layers. As illustrated, these interfaces interact with the:

1. Telemetry Data Collector (TDCME) in the Orchestration Layer to dynamically record the collected telemetry data
2. AI Forecaster in the AI Layer to store forecasting results
3. Application Development Layer to share forecasted telemetry data with the Application Controller or code objects with the Application Programming Model (APM)
4. Virtual Training Environment (VTE) to provide it with datasets for AI training

The Data Manager provides data management, authentication and authorization services, while the Data Stores are used for the distributed storage of data and objects.

Figure 1: Data Layer position in ENACT Architecture

6. Technical Components

This section presents the technical implementation of the ENACT Data Layer, which is premised upon the concept of Data Spaces. Data Spaces are defined as “a federated, open infrastructure for sovereign data sharing, based on common policies, rules and standards” [1]. They are designed to enable the secure sharing, interoperability of data among different stakeholders while maintaining data sovereignty. Unlike traditional centralized data platforms, Data Spaces enable data providers to retain control over their data while participating in a shared ecosystem. Each participant contributes and accesses data according to clearly defined rules and governance models.

From a technical perspective, a Data Space is the collection of system components that enable the sovereign exchange of assets among participants. In that regard, the first reference architecture has been established by the International Data Spaces Association (IDSA); it is called IDSA Reference Architecture Model [2] and provides the specifications for implementing Data Spaces. It defines the main roles (such as participants that are users acting as asset providers and/or asset consumers, and intermediaries which offer trusted services within a dataspace like metadata management), components (like connectors, identity providers, and brokers).

Data Space Connectors constitute the core component in Data Spaces and inevitably, a key enabling technology to build the ENACT Data Space. In principle, Data Connectors serve as the gateway for

participants to connect to a Data Space, providing mechanisms for secure data discovery, sharing and transfer, automating contract negotiations on data usage and facilitating the enforcement of access and data governance policies.

Essentially, Data Space Connectors enable the data sharing between data providers and data consumers. A data provider acts as the source connection, offering data assets or services while retaining ownership and control over how and by whom the data is accessed. The data client, on the other hand, can discover and consume these data assets based on the agreed usage contracts and policies. This exchange process within the Data Space ensures that data is shared securely and transparently, respecting the sovereignty of data providers.

Overall, Data Spaces foster data federation and transparency while ensuring that data providers retain control over by whom and under which conditions their data is accessed and used.

The ENACT Data Space supports the storage, discovery, and controlled exchange of both data and objects among different CCC components and participants, providing dynamic and secure data management mechanisms.

ENACT also extends the conventional concept of Data Spaces to allow for the sharing of code objects, such as executable scripts, that can be retrieved by the ENACT SDK during application development. This constitutes a key ENACT innovation that promotes the collaboration and sharing among developers, thus enabling objects’ re-usability and accelerating application development.

The ENACT distributed data storage system currently comprises three different nodes hosted at CERTH, UNP and UPV premises. The available nodes are summarized in Table 1 and used for the storage and sharing of historical telemetry data, pilot data and code objects as shown in Figure 2.

Node	Technologies Used	Purpose	Storage Capacity
CERTH Server	MinIO	Storage of historic telemetry data, pilot metadata and code objects; Compatible with dataspace connectors	3 TB
UPV Node	Elasticsearch	Indexed storage of metrics and logs	20 GB
UNP Cluster	MinIO, Apache Kafka, PostgreSQL	Testing and integration	Master node: 8 GB Worker nodes: 8 GB, 16 GB, 32 GB

Table 1: ENACT Distributed Storage Nodes

Figure 2: ENACT Distributed Storage Overview

The next development steps (to take place in WP7) involve extending the current deployment with additional distributed storage nodes.

6.1 Data Access and Sharing Interfaces

6.1.1 Overview

The Data Access and Sharing Interfaces are responsible for sharing assets securely, accessing and retrieving data and objects from the distributed data stores. This is achieved through Dataspace Connectors and APIs used to enable CRUD operations.

6.1.2 Technological Description

After investigating the available connector distributions, the soivity connector was selected as the most suitable implementation for the ENACT purposes. Soivity¹ builds upon the EDC Connector², which is fully compliant with IDS³ and Gaia-X⁴ specifications. It ensures secure communication, expressing and enforcing usage control rules through Open Digital Rights Language (ODRL), and support identity management via both bespoke centralized IDS identity authorities through the Dynamic Attribute Provisioning Service (DAPS) and decentralized identity management approaches, using decentralized identifiers (DIDs) and verifiable credentials (VCs).

The soivity connector enhances the EDC Connector's capabilities by providing enterprise-grade managed services, such as the "Connector-as-a-Service", a service that facilitates participants to join existing dataspaces.

¹ <https://soivity.de/en/soivity-en/>

² <https://github.com/eclipse-edc/Connector>

³ <https://docs.internationaldataspaces.org/ids-knowledgebase/dataspace-protocol>

⁴ <https://docs.gaia-x.eu/policy-rules-committee/compliance-document/25.03/pdf/document.pdf>

Our implementation leverages the soviety Community Edition EDC⁵, which is integrated with a User Interface (UI), the so-called soviety EDC UI⁶, thus facilitating manual management and monitoring. They are both available as Docker Images, which makes them ready-to-use and rather easily deployable. Moreover, they are customizable and extensible, hence allowing for configuring them according to the project needs.

Building upon the soviety EDC Dataspace Connectors, the sharing of ENACT assets is achieved via the soviety UI following the stepwise process illustrated in Figure 3. As shown, the user interact with the connectors through the management API endpoint, while the connectors intercommunicate via their dataspace protocol API endpoints.

Figure 3: Asset sharing workflow through soviety connectors

The exact steps to offer an asset (asset and policy creation, contract definition) and to consume available assets are described in detail below:

First of all, access policies and contract policies must be defined on the data provider side. The former specify the conditions under which a data offer is visible to other Data Space participants, while the latter refer to the conditions under which the data can be consumed. By default, three types of restrictions can be defined in soviety Community Edition EDC:

- Unrestricted access/use of assets (“always-true” policy)
- Validating the time of negotiation/data transfer, thus data consumption is subject to specific date/time restrictions.
- Limiting data offers to specific valid durations.
- Data offer access restricted to specific consumer participant IDs.

⁵ <https://github.com/soviety/edc-ce>

⁶ <https://github.com/soviety/edc-ui>

Those restrictions can also be combined to create a policy expression using the 'AND', 'OR' and 'XONE' operators (Figure 4).

Figure 4: soivity EDC UI - Policy Creation

Data offers for the ENACT assets can be discovered by eligible client connector instances through their catalog browser (Figure 5).

Figure 5: soivity EDC UI - Client Catalog Browser

Then the client can negotiate the offer. When clicking on the 'Negotiate' button, an automatic contract negotiation process is initiated, and once completed successfully, a contract will appear under the "Contracts" tab, on both the provider and consumer side (Figure 6).

Figure 6: soivity EDC UI - Contracts

As a final step, the consumer can click on Transfer to request fetching the actual data. The consumer will then be prompted to provide a URL pointing to its data sink (Figure 7).

Figure 7: soivity EDC UI - Client Initiating Transfer dialog

After providing its data sink details and initiating the transfer, it will be automatically verified that a valid contract exists and the corresponding policies are satisfied; if so, the data transfer from the defined data source to the client’s data sink will be executed (Figure 8).

Figure 8: soivity EDC UI - Transfer History

Furthermore, we rely on the soivity DAPS⁷, which is premised upon a Keycloak IAM service⁸. The DAPS is used as the central identity provider, providing each connector with unique credentials to be used during their intercommunication.

ENACT allows for the execution of these steps also through a custom Node.js API. For this purpose, a collection of API requests guiding users step-by-step has been developed. This setup enables dynamic registration of multiple EDC connector instances, allowing different Data Space participants to deploy their own connectors while maintaining dynamic management of the connectors. More specifically, participants can register their own EDC connectors through the API, providing connector

⁷ <https://github.com/soivity/soivity-daps>

⁸ <https://www.keycloak.org/>

details such as management URLs, DSP endpoints, and authentication credentials. The API handles centrally routing requests to appropriate connectors, health monitoring, and secure credential management with encrypted storage.

6.1.3 Development Status

As of project M18, the ENACT Data Space has been deployed successfully, while its extension with more distributed nodes is in progress and expected to be completed by the end of the project.

At the current stage, we have set up the soivity connectors to expose data offers from the data sources considered in ENACT. To achieve so, the assets to be offered need to be created. For this purpose, upon asset creation on the provider connector side, assets are connected to a specific source by defining the relevant API endpoint from which the connector retrieves the assets. In our case, this can be either an endpoint being used by the telemetry data collection service or one connected to the SDK for exchanging objects (Figure 9: ENACT data sourceFigure 9).

Figure 9: ENACT data source

Upon assets creation, relevant data offers need to be made, including the created assets and policies. To allow all ENACT Data Space participants to access the ENACT assets without any restrictions, we mainly use the “always-true” policy.

Moreover, a dedicated Keycloak server has been set up (as described later in 6.2.2.121) and the connectors have been configured accordingly to interconnect with our instance for authentication purposes.

In addition, a custom Node.js API has been developed to dynamically manage multiple EDC connector instances. This API supports dynamic connector registration, secure credential management with

encryption, health monitoring, and proxy functionality for routing requests to appropriate connectors and audit logging. The API has been integrated with the Keycloak authenticator.

Some indicative endpoints offered by the API to perform associated operations are listed in Table 2:

API Endpoint	Description
GET /api/v1/connector/status	Get connector status
GET /api/v1/connector/catalog	Get connector catalog
GET /api/v1/assets/:id	Get asset by ID
POST /api/v1/assets	Create a new asset
PUT /api/v1/assets/:id	Update an asset
DELETE /api/v1/assets/:id	Delete an asset
GET /api/v1/objects/:id	Get object by ID
PUT /api/v1/objects/:id	Update object metadata
DELETE /api/v1/objects/:id	Delete an object
GET /api/v1/objects/:id/download	Download an object
POST /api/v1/edc/contractnegotiations	Initiate contract negotiation
GET /api/v1/edc/contractnegotiations/:id	Get contract negotiation status
POST /api/v1/edc/transfers	Initiate data transfer
POST /api/v1/policies	Create a policy
POST /api/v1/contractdefinitions	Create a contract definition
Connector Management	
POST /api/connectors/register	Register new EDC connector instance
GET /api/connectors	List all registered connectors
GET /api/connectors/:id	Get specific connector details
POST /api/connectors/health	Health check all registered connectors
DELETE /api/connectors/:id	Deactivate a connector
Data Transfer Handling	
POST /api/v1/data-exchange/data-receiver	Receive data transfers from EDC connectors
GET /api/v1/data-exchange/stored-data	List stored transferred data
GET /api/v1/data-exchange/stored-data/:filename	Download specific stored data

Table 2: Connector API Endpoints

The above endpoints exposed by the API are used for the interconnection between the provider connector instances and the relevant data sources. Data transfers from EDC connectors are automatically processed and stored in MinIO object storage with comprehensive metadata tracking. The implementation includes production-ready features such as encrypted credential storage, automated health monitoring, audit logging, and resilient error handling with retry mechanisms.

During the implementation of the Data Access and Sharing Interfaces, we encountered several technical challenges, including handling request bodies in asset creation operations, retrieving negotiation IDs correctly, and supporting multiple authentication methods, which required developing additional solutions, such as field validation and format checking or specialized response handlers, to be resolved. Furthermore, mock mode was enabled to eliminate any technical silos stemming from the need for live EDC instances and allow for testing and development even when EDC services might be unavailable.

6.2 Data Manager

6.2.1 Overview

The Data Manager includes two subcomponents, namely the Security and Access Control Manager and the Metadata Manager, responsible for identity and access management and for metadata handling, respectively. It also supports Monitoring Services, which are used to track the health of EDC endpoints and to provide associated diagnostics.

6.2.2 Technological Description

6.2.2.1 Security and Access Control Manager

To provide authentication and authorization services, the ENACT Security and Access Control Manager is based on Keycloak, a widely used IAM platform, suitable for user creation, management and credentials verification. Keycloak eliminates the need for integrating services with login forms, storing users and credentials. It provides an off-the-shelf customizable platform to secure applications and services, allowing for easily managing users, controlling user permissions and enforcing fine-grained access policies.

In ENACT, we have deployed a Keycloak server accessible at <https://enact-auth.iti.gr>. Once activated, the management of users and their assignment to ENACT is being handled through the admin console. The Keycloak authenticator has been integrated with the connectors through the following configuration steps:

1. **Realm Creation:** We created a dedicated "DAPS" realm to bind the Keycloak server with the ENACT connectors. A realm is essentially an independent set of users, credentials, roles and groups, functioning as a tenant for our dataspace participants.
2. **Client Scopes Configuration:** Then, relevant client scopes were set up. Scopes determine the set of attributes to be requested from the DAPS. An `idsc:IDS_CONNECTOR_ATTRIBUTES_ALL` scope, which includes all IDS Attributes available to the DAPS, has been created. In this step, we consider the OpenID Connect protocol for identity management.
3. **Connector Client Registration:** The participants (providers and consumers) have to be added. In Keycloak, participants are represented as service accounts. Therefore, client service accounts for participants were created. For example:
 - Client ID: connector-1
 - Client authentication: Enabled
 - Authorization: Enabled
 - Service accounts: Enabled for machine-to-machine communication
4. **Role Definition:** Two specific roles were created for EDC integration:
 - edc-user: Standard user role for basic connector operations
 - edc-admin: Administrative role for advanced connector management

The interconnection between data providers and consumers in the ENACT Data Space utilizes OAuth2/OpenID Connect flows. Registered participants acquire Dynamic Attribute Tokens (DAT) via a CURL command, like so:

```
curl -X POST https://enact-auth.iti.gr/realms/DAPS/protocol/openid-connect/token \
-d "client_id=connector-1" \
-d "client_secret=<Client Secret>" \
-d "grant_type=password" \
-d "username=<username>" \
-d "password=<pwd>"
```

ENACT applications and users are thereafter managed within this specific DAPS realm. The interconnection between data providers and consumers in the ENACT Data Space utilizes OAuth2/OpenID Connect flows, as illustrated in Figure 10. Once registered in the sovity DAPS, both provider and consumer connectors acquire DATs which are then used during communication to automatically authenticate participants.

Figure 10: Trusted Communication Establishment between Provider and Consumer Connectors

6.2.2.2 Metadata Manager

The Metadata Manager enriches the stored assets with metadata information, such as asset id, address etc. Based on such metadata, it supports indexing/de-indexing and filtering functions for linking stored assets to distributed data stores, and facilitating the retrieval of matching data upon requests.

6.3 Data Stores

6.3.1 Overview

The ENACT Data Stores correspond to nodes and/or devices distributed across the ENACT continuum. Three distributed storage nodes have been deployed and provided by CERTH, UNP, and UPV (as shown before, in Figure 2). Each one supports different storage technologies, including MinIO for high-performance object storage, Elasticsearch for distributed storage and data indexing, and Apache Kafka combined with PostgreSQL for fast data streaming and ingestion. As storage requirements evolve based on the specific needs identified by the pilot use cases and component leaders, new nodes will be added to the ENACT Data Space.

6.3.2 Technological Description

Prior to setting up the data stores, we circulated a questionnaire in order to identify the actual project storage needs (see Annex: Questionnaire on Storage Needs). The overall purpose of this questionnaire was to gather input from pilots and technical leaders regarding their specific requirements that are anticipated to be addressed from the storage system. Therefore, we created a set of pertinent questions on relevant topics, such as the types of data they would generate, their expected data volumes, the types of storage nodes (e.g. cloud, edge, on partner premises), any specific security requirements (e.g. encryption or anonymization) and any particular storage needs (e.g. creating dedicated databases, preferred storage technologies etc). Another objective of the questionnaire was to identify whether there are any certain storage nodes that are already setup and managed by partners and expected to be connected to the ENACT continuum. By collecting this information, we aimed at assessing the operational requirements in terms of storage and determine the most suitable distributed storage technologies. This process was essential to guide the selection and deployment of storage nodes tailored to the specific demands of ENACT.

As shown in Figure 12, we received 7 valid responses to the questionnaire, out of which 4 were from component leaders (UOWM, CERTH, ICE, DNET) and 3 were from pilot partners (MOG, OSO, FUJ). The answers were given from technical partners that require persistent storage. Those are mostly the partners leading the components that will be directly interacting with the Data Layer in the ENACT architecture (specifically, TDCME form UOWM, AI Forecaster from CERTH, Application Controller & VTE from ICE) (as depicted Figure 1).

Figure 12: Questionnaire respondents

The respective decisions derived about the actual implementation based on the analysis of the collected input are described below:

WHERE WILL DATA BE STORED?

- Cloud
- On premises, but access will be granted to partners
- Clusters/along with deployed application
- ENACT data stores

Figure 13: Answers to "Where will data be stored?"

One of the main question was “Where will data be stored?”. It came up that most partners want to store the generated data on the cloud. Also, many of the respondents answered that the data will be hosted along with the deployed applications. One storage node will also be provided by a use-case partner who will set it up on its own premises but grant access to ENACT partners. Those are summarized in Figure 13.

- The volume of data is expected to be relatively modest, typically in the range of megabytes (MBs), though in some cases it may grow to several gigabytes (GBs). The types of data to be stored include application performance metrics, infrastructure metrics, time series data. For the use cases, data such as video/audio streams, participants’ feedback and analytics and platform snapshots might be considered (this is further analyzed in 7.327).

- Four partners have indicated the need for a database to support their storage requirements. Lastly, four partners have requested the use of ENACT resources for the hosting and management of their respective storage solutions.

The data stores/nodes distributed in the ENACT continuum for storing data are then being selected with the aim to cover the storage requirements identified by this brief survey. In particular the following nodes and storage technologies have been deployed:

- UPV node: To address the needs for distributed, scalable and indexed asset storing, we rely upon **Elasticsearch**. Elasticsearch has been selected for storing metrics and logs info from the ENACT continuum because of its efficient full-text search capabilities, flexible data modeling, near real-time indexing and multi-cluster configuration. These features enable fast querying and analysis of large volumes of both structured and unstructured data. Its scalability and powerful aggregation support make it a suitable choice for handling observability, monitoring, and analytical workloads across varied datasets. This node offers 20GB of storage space.
- CERTH server: For extending the storage system to support code object sharing, the system integrates **MinIO**. MinIO is a high-performance, S3-compatible object storage solution for large-scale data storage and retrieval. It supports efficient handling of unstructured data such as code artifacts and binaries, automatically organizing and storing data with comprehensive metadata including transfer timestamps, source connector information, and data provenance tracking, making it well-suited for collaborative and distributed development environments. MinIO also facilitates the automatic storage and retrieval of data exchanged through the EDC connectors. This node offers 3TB for storage.
- UNP cluster: The cluster provided by UNP is being currently used by several components and use cases for testing and integration purposes. This cluster is equipped with MinIO for object

storage, but also **Apache Kafka**¹¹ and **PostgreSQL**¹² for data streaming and persistent storage. Apache Kafka enables real-time data ingestion and event streaming between distributed components, while PostgreSQL offers a structured database for long-term storing. The cluster consists of a master node with 8GB storage capacity, and three worker nodes with storage capacity 8GB, 16GB, and 32GB, respectively.

6.3.3 Development Status

Elasticsearch instances have been set up as storage nodes in the ENACT continuum. Those instances have been deployed using the Helm chart¹³ and with the following configurations:

- One master node per deployment.
- Authentication enabled. Ensures that all the users that have access to the information have the proper credentials.
- Configure SSL to prevent man-in-the-middle attacks and traffic sniffing.

Apart from this, the following storage features have also been configured:

- Maximum 20GB of space for metrics and logs volumes.
- Once the maximum is achieved a new volume is created.
- The old volume data is removed once the data is older than 10 days.

This configuration ensures the storage of historical data from the last 20 days of ENACT continuum activity, without being affected by Elasticsearch's performance or storage requirements.

The actual development could be finalized pending the feedback and new future requirements from other ENACT components like the ones in the AI layer needs more historical data or it is needed to increase any other configuration it will be added using the same Helm chart but with these new features available.

For accessing the Elasticsearch API endpoints to populate and query data from an Elasticsearch client, we have developed a Python script that supports:

- Index Management: Create, delete, and check the existence of Elasticsearch indices with custom mappings.
- Document Deletion: Delete certain documents by ID or perform bulk deletions of documents that match a specified query
- Data Ingestion: Populate indices with data (e.g., from CSV files)
- Custom query time intervals: Specify fixed time intervals for queries and update query time range

¹¹ <https://kafka.apache.org/>

¹² <https://www.postgresql.org/>

¹³ <https://github.com/elastic/helm-charts/tree/main/elasticsearch>

- Query-based Search: Execute search queries and get back search hits that match the query using custom request bodies
- Kibana Integration: The script supports KQL queries for compatibility with Kibana dashboards

Regarding the MinIO storage, a MinIO instance has been deployed and integrated with the connector API for handling EDC data transfers:

- The system automatically processes incoming data transfers and converts them to structured JSON format
- Incoming data are then stored along with metadata for retrieval and analysis. The storage includes configurable retention policies and supports both manual and automated data retrieval through the API endpoints (described in Table 2).

Figure 14An example of storing ENACT assets in the deployed MinIO store is depicted in Figure 14.

Figure 14: ENACT MinIO object store in CERTH server

7. Use cases & Integration

7.1 Interconnections with ENACT components

7.1.1 Telemetry Data Collector & Monitoring Engine

Through TDCME, real-time metrics are collected in terms of computational, networking and energy aspects of distributed applications. Historical telemetry data collection spans compute network energy and application services, which gives detailed insights into Kubernetes-based workload operations. The system maintains scalability through local data processing, which reduces the need for extensive domain-based information exchange.

The ENACT Data Layer receives metrics from TDCME for storage and distribution to index and enrich the data before service availability. Through its integration with the Data Spaces, TDCME is offered a mechanism for the secure distribution of structured telemetry data between ENACT tenants and

domains. The historical data provides insights into distributed application behaviour and assists in the training of AI models to better understand the underlying peculiarities of distributed applications. The architecture design of both components enables interoperability and extensibility capabilities, which reduce operational complexity.

To integrate the TDCME component with the Data Space, two connectors are up and running, one Provider Connector on UOWM side and one Consumer Connector at CERTH's end. Those connectors have been registered to the ENACT Keycloak authentication service and acquired relevant tokens which are embedded in their following actions so that they are automatically authenticated.

Both connectors are deployed and accessible locally via their respective dashboards. The provision of historical telemetry data by the provider and its retrieval and storage by the consumer are realized following the steps described in 6.1.3. In particular, as a first step, the provider (UOWM) creates a policy defining the conditions and permissions under which the data can be shared. For instance, a uowm-data policy is created that does not impose any restrictions to data usage (Figure 15).

Figure 15: uowm-data policy creation

Next, the provider registers the data asset (e.g. uowm-data) that will be made available for exchange and creates an associated data offer for such assets under the terms of the uowm-data policy. While creating the data offer, relevant TDCME endpoints are defined as the data source by explicitly specifying the public URL exposing the collected metrics. For instance, in Figure 16, the data source is the endpoint `/pod/{pod_name}/{container_name}/metrics` (wherein `pod_name` and `container_name` are defined appropriately) to fetch the CPU and memory metrics of a container inside a specific pod, and is accessible through port 8081 of UOWM's public IP.

Figure 16: Data offer for TDCME data

This offer becomes discoverable by the consumer (CERTH) which uses its catalog browser to view and select the data offer published by UOWM and initiates a contract negotiation for TDCME’s data offer (Figure 17).

Figure 17: Negotiating TDCME's data offer

Upon successful negotiation, a contract is established, which then appears under the "Contracts" tab of the consumer connector dashboard. CERTH specifies the MinIO endpoint URL that will receive the data to complete the process and initiates the data transfer.

Figure 18: Transferring TDCME data to Data Space

The data is successfully transferred from TDCME to the MinIO store, completing the data exchange.

7.2 Application Programming Model

The Application Programming Model (APM) serves as a critical backend component designed to support secure and standardized data interactions within a broader data-driven ecosystem. It works in tandem with the SDK to streamline the development of applications and interact with cloud storage infrastructures such as MinIO.

The SDK offers a simplified interface to assist developers in rapidly generating both data processing and data upload scripts. The APM provides essential backend logic, particularly for secure data transfer and authentication, while the SDK encapsulates these functions in a developer-friendly way, abstracting sensitive operations from the application logic. This modular separation ensures that while the SDK enhances developer productivity, the APM retains full control over critical operations like data integrity, secure uploads, and service authentication.

The Data Layer intercommunicates with the Application Programming Model (APM) to support object sharing through Data Space connectors. In principle, the APM acts as an intermediary between the Data Space and the SDK. In this respect, the APM sends and application metadata generated by the SDK to be stored at the Data Layer. The stored code objects are later available to other developers and can be re-used as templates to facilitate application development. Therefore, by enabling object sharing through its Data Space, the ENACT project not only accelerates the application development process but also fosters the collaboration and sovereign knowledge transfer between developers.

Figure 19: APM-Data Space interaction for code object storing

7.2.1 AI Forecaster & Application Controller

The AI Forecaster sends the forecasted telemetry data to the Data Layer to be stored so that it can be used for application-level optimizations as well as future AI training sessions. The stored predictions are later retrieved by the Application Controller to be taken into account in the deployment optimizations performed at the application level. The associated workflow is shown in the sequence diagram in

Figure 20.

The past forecasted telemetry data are also used by the Virtual Training Environment to update the AI models and feed them back to the AI Forecaster (the interaction with the VTE is described in 7.2.2).

Figure 20: Data Layer-AI Forecaster & Application Controller Interactions

7.2.2 Virtual Training Environment

The Virtual Training Environment interacts with the Data Layer to retrieve either historical telemetry data or past forecasting results to be used in AI model training, as shown in Figure 21.

Figure 21: Data Layer-VTE Interaction

7.3 Data Space Integration into Pilot UCs

The main objective of integrating the ENACT Data Space into the pilots is to store the respective telemetry data that are collected during the monitoring of pilot applications through the TDCME component. This will enable the creation of a Data Space interconnected with different monitoring sources, concentrating a large amount of historical telemetry data that can provide a rich dataset to be fed in VTE for boosting AI training.

Apart from this, the distributed ENACT data storage system will be used for storing application metadata and generated objects in order to facilitate their re-usability, deployment and distribution across the ENACT CCC.

7.3.1 UC#1: Media Broadcasting: Hyper-distributed Media Content Processing

In the context of this use case, the integration with the data layer will be considered in case of need to store or index AI-generated video metadata, the Data Access & Sharing Interfaces and the Data Manager components will be integrated. These components may be incorporated at the stage where enriched media content is generated and needs to be stored for efficient retrieval. The data layer will facilitate the organized storage of metadata, enabling efficient search capabilities and controlled access to the content. Potential data sources to be stored include AI event detection video output and metadata generated during the video analysis process. This integration will ensure that metadata can be indexed and managed effectively.

Moreover, telemetry data on the performance of broadcasting applications will be collected and stored in the Data Space to be considered in AI training and orchestration optimizations.

7.3.2 UC#2: Enhanced Live Experience: Transforming rowing Regattas La Cocha Flag Tracking with VR Technologies

The integration of the Data Layer in use case 2 is currently being considered with the aim to improve the live streaming experience. The Data layer can be used to temporarily store selected data flows —such as GPS signals, QoS/QoE metrics (latency, jitter, rebuffering events), and contextual metadata from video/audio transmissions— collected during the La Cocha Flag regatta event live streaming. This would allow the system to better handle short-term buffering or to recover from momentary data losses, thus contributing to improved streaming sessions. In addition, the streaming applications will be monitored and the collected telemetry data will be stored to enable enhanced orchestration of the streaming services and ultimately, an enhanced streaming experience.

On a long-term basis, the Data Layer can be leveraged to extend the pilot's capabilities with features such as asynchronous on-demand viewing, interactive replay functionalities, or providing performance analytics, which are beyond the current pilot scope.

7.3.3 UC#3: Hyper-distributed Data Processing for Fujitsu's Mobility Digital Twin Initiative

- The technologies considered for storing data that are either consumed by the pilot or related to the pilot deployment include Kafka, PostgreSQL, MinIO, and Keycloak. More specifically: Kafka is storing input and output data, where input data are structured messages that are ready to be processed by main component Dracena which is run as an Apache Flink job and task. Output contains structured messages that are processed and ready to be displayed. Kafka is using standard persistentVolume/persistentVolumeClaim resources. Messages contain granular, open data information about the GPS positions of public transport vehicles, weather conditions and air quality information. No sensitive data is kept.
- PostgreSQL – used in Integra (frontend) component for storing settings of each user
- MinIO – object storage where dracena.jar file is kept due to licensing cannot be stored on open storage or committed into git, other than that we might use it for snapshots of Apache Flink jobs' state.
- Keycloak – contains users' account settings for the frontend component.

This storage system has been tested in the cluster hosted in UNP's premises, which can be used as an ENACT storage node for pilot data. The interconnection with the storage services offered in this

cluster can be achieved using soivity connectors to allow for seamless integration with the ENACT data space. That way, pilot-generated data will be stored in a distributed way, including jar files representing digital twin snapshots that can be easily retrieved for application deployment across the CCC or as code templates by the ENACT SDK. The distributed storage of pilot applications' snapshots is also useful to restore the latest running states and facilitate application re-deployment in case of disaster scenarios.

Last but not least, monitoring of telemetry data concerning the applications deployed within this pilot, are being collected using the TDCME component to provide metrics and traces which will be stored at the distributed Data Stores. Such data will then be fed to the AI Layer to be leveraged during deployment optimization and orchestration.

7.3.4 Storing SDK-generated video streaming application metadata in the ENACT Data Space

Early integration of the APM with the Data Layer is currently being piloted in collaboration with MOG and consists of two distinct workflows. Each workflow demonstrates a different stage in the video data lifecycle, from processing raw media to securely storing derived metadata in a data space. In particular, the first workflow corresponds to storing video metadata that has been extracted by the SDK to the Data Space, while the second one corresponds to the retrieval and consumption of the stored data. The interaction with the Data Layer is achieved through soivity connectors, as delineated below.

Workflow 1: Asset uploading to ENACT Data Space

The first workflow outlines how a user utilizes the SDK to process and upload video data in a secure, modular, and policy-compliant manner. This workflow demonstrates the interplay between the SDK and the APM, where the SDK is responsible for generating high-level scripts, while the APM module encapsulates sensitive logic such as authorization, validation, and data transfer.

As illustrated in Figure 22, the process begins when the user opens the Eclipse IDE and initializes a Java project. Through the SDK interface, the user selects an option to create a new script for video processing and upload. The SDK then triggers a code generation routine, producing a Java class that encapsulates logic for video analysis and metadata extraction.

Figure 22: Workflow 1: Data Uploading

Following successful local execution of the processing script, the user moves on to the upload phase. The SDK provides a second code generation feature that creates a secure upload script, which internally calls the APM Upload Module. This module first initiates a validation step to ensure that the user has the required permissions to upload the data. Validation is handled through a Sovity EDC Provider Connector, deployed on Siemens' end, which manages communication with the data space and handles contract negotiation. The connector requests a contract offer and awaits a response. If the contract is granted, the APM proceeds with the upload to MiniIO. If permission is denied, the module raises a validation error and aborts the operation.

After a successful upload, the APM automatically updates the connector's catalog with the new asset metadata, ensuring discoverability and future access control. The user is abstracted away from all low-level operations such as credential handling, endpoint configuration, and contract negotiation — all of which are encapsulated within the APM logic. By embedding policy validation directly within the APM, this workflow achieves a higher level of security and conformance to data space principles. The SDK maintains its role as a lightweight development facilitator, while the APM takes full responsibility for secure interactions with external services.

This approach ensures:

- **Security**, by enforcing access control before upload
- **Modularity**, by cleanly separating UI, generation logic, and upload logic

- **Usability**, by allowing users to operate through a simplified interface without handling sensitive logic

Workflow 2: Asset retrieval from ENACT Data Space

The second workflow focuses on the secure and validated retrieval of data from the MinIO cloud storage, emphasizing access governance in the connectors and download execution via the APM. This complements the first workflow by allowing authorized users to retrieve previously uploaded datasets while maintaining compliance with data space policies.

As shown in Figure 23, the process begins when the user opens the Eclipse IDE and interacts with the SDK to initiate a new data download script. The user defines the necessary configuration parameters, such as the asset identifier or MinIO bucket name.

Figure 23: Workflow 2: Data retrieval

Upon script generation, the SDK delegates execution to the APM Download Module, which is responsible for both validating access and retrieving the data. The APM integrates an embedded EDC Consumer Connector, deployed on SIE's side, which communicates with the Provider Connector hosted by CERTH via Sovity's data space infrastructure. The APM issues a contract offer request based on the user's access credentials and the asset configuration.

This interaction is governed by the Connector's Data Offer mechanism. As shown in Figure 24, each data offer includes:

- A unique asset reference (e.g., access-to-video-8465)
- An associated access policy
- A contract policy, both of which define the terms of data usage.

Figure 24: Video Data Offer

In this case, the "always-true" policy is applied for demonstration purposes, allowing unrestricted access. The corresponding policy structure is shown in Figure 25, where the USE action is explicitly permitted under ODRL-compliant terms.

Figure 25: Connector Usage Policy

If the provider connector approves the access request, it responds with a metadata JSON file detailing the storage structure and location of the data within MinIO. This asset is further described in Figure 26, where tags such as video, histogram, and MinIO provide semantic insight into the data's nature.

Figure 26: Retrieved Asset

Once access is granted and metadata received, the APM parses the response and proceeds to securely download the data to the user's local system. If access is denied, the APM terminates the operation and returns a detailed error.

The SDK remains abstracted away from these internal steps, providing a high-level interface and orchestrating script generation. This architectural separation ensures:

- **Policy enforcement** is handled by the connectors,
- **Secure execution** and validation occur within the APM,
- **Usability** is preserved through SDK automation.

8. Release Summary

Component	Subcomponent	Release Information	Details and Links
Data Access & Sharing Interfaces	sovity EDC Connectors	Version	10.3.0
		Source Code	https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/enact-project/data-access-and-sharing-interfaces
		Binaries	-
		Documentation	https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/enact-project/data-access-and-sharing-interfaces/-/blob/main/README.md
		Docker Image	-
		Dependencies	-
	Node.js API	Version	1.0.0
		Source Code	https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/enact-project/data-access-and-sharing-interfaces/-/tree/enact-api-connector
		Binaries	-
		Documentation	https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/enact-project/data-access-and-sharing-interfaces/-/blob/enact-api-connector/README.md
		Docker Image	-
		Dependencies	sovity EDC CE Connectors

Component	Subcomponent	Release Information	Details and Links
Data Manager	esmanager.py	Version	1.0.0
		Source Code	https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/enact-project/data-manager/-/tree/es_manager
		Binaries	-
		Documentation	https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/enact-project/data-manager/-/blob/es_manager/README.md
		Docker Image	-
		Dependencies	-

9. Conclusions

This deliverable introduces the first concrete implementation of the ENACT Data Space. It describes in an extensive manner the ENACT Data Layer components, i.e., the Data Access & Sharing Interfaces, the Data Manager and the distributed Data Stores. In particular, D4.3 documents the technological background and the development status of each functional component as of M18.

It presents how these components will be integrated into ENACT and interact with the TDCME, Application Programming Model, Application Controller, AI Forecaster and Virtual Training Environment components to enable secure and sovereign data and objects sharing across the ENACT CCC. Furthermore, it describes the integration of the distributed ENACT data storage system in the three pilot applications in order to create a store of the respective telemetry metrics and forecasts to assist in AI training, but also to facilitate pilot application deployment and improved performance.

The development of the technical advancements presented in D4.3 will be continued in WP7 with the aim to fully address the defined functional requirements as well as to perform any necessary refinements based on feedback from the pilot activities.

10. References

- [1] A. Reiberg, N. Crispin and K. Peter, "What is a data space.," *White Paper 1*, 2022.
- [2] B. Otto, S. Steinbuß, A. Teuscher and S. Lohmann, "IDS Reference Architecture Model (Version 3.0)," 2019. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5105529>.

11. Annex: Questionnaire on Storage Needs

A snapshot of the questionnaire is illustrated in Figure 27- Figure 29.

ENACT Data storage

This questionnaire has been created in the context of T4.4 to identify the ENACT storage needs

Section 1

...

1. Partner ID *

- CETH
- ICE
- MDG
- FLJ
- EITB
- OSO
- INNO
- UCWM
- SIE
- UPV
- FDI
- ICCS
- DNET
- DS4
- UNP
- ARCTUR
- ECL

2. Answering as a *

- UC leader
- Component leader
- Other

Figure 27: Data Storage questionnaire (Questions 1,2)

3. What kind of data do you need to be stored?

Enter your answer

4. What is the format of the data? (e.g. json, yaml etc)

Enter your answer

5. What is the expected data size?

KBs

MBs

GBs

6. Are there any sensitive data considered? If so, which data is that?

Enter your answer

7. Are there any particular data security needs to be taken into account? (e.g. data needs to be anonymized, or encrypted)

Enter your answer

8. Where will data be stored?

Cloud

On premises, but access will be granted to partners

Other

9. Are there any particular storage needs that have to be addressed by ENACT data store nodes (e.g. create a DB, host on cloud etc)?

Enter your answer

10. If you answered YES at the previous question: will you be responsible for the setup, host and management of the DB/node?

Yes

No, I need ENACT resources

Figure 28: Data Storage questionnaire (Questions 3-10)

Section 2 ...

Pilot data

Pilot leaders, please answer also the below questions.

11. What are the considered data sources? For both real and simulated data.

Enter your answer

12. Will any open datasets be considered? If YES, specify which ones.

Enter your answer

13. Are you generating any data? If YES, what kind of data will you generate and for what purpose?

Enter your answer

Figure 29: Data Storage questionnaire (Questions on pilot data)